

The Odisha Official Language Act and Language Movement in 21st Century Ad

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ABSTRACT

The Odia language, since its inception has played a significant role in establishing the uniqueness of the people of Odisha. In the 12th century AD Chodagangadev of Eastern-Ganga family has established "Sakalatkola" and made the Odia language the dominant speech in this land. In 15th century AD the great pioneer of Odia Identity 'Kapilendradev' used the word 'Odisha' and introduced 'Odia' as the Official Language in his empire. After 1568 this community has lost the hard earned Identity and this was again restored in 1936 with the creation of Odisha state on Language basis. After introduction of Indian Constitution in 1950 the provision in Art.345-351 resulted in the "The Orissa Official language Act, 1954". Though we got the Act for the use of Odia Language in all official purposes of Odisha still we are thousand miles behind the achievement of 'Kapilendradev' in 15th Century AD. Now in the 21st Century after 71 years of the establishment of democracy in India, 'Black Flag march' have been organising in the banner of 'Bhasa Andolan' every day since 13-04-2016 till date. After amendment and official notifications it is still to be implemented in the real term of the above Act in Odisha. In this paper emphasis is given on the attempts made to implement the above Act; the successes and failures, stumbling blocks on path; necessity of the use of Odia Language in administration and the relevance of present day Odia Language Movement in Odisha. The study is qualitative and descriptive in nature basing upon secondary data.

KEYWORDS: Odia Language, Odisha Official Language Act, Odia Identity, Language movement

1. INTRODUCTION

The geographical lands, the people, the Language, the Culture we are living in are the contributions of our ancestors. The Odia Language and Culture have united the people of this land previously segregated as Odra, Utkala, Kalinga, Kongada and Kosala . The Odia language in the process of evolution took its concrete form in 10th century AD and during that period the Somavamsi rulers united all the independent kingdoms politically and culturally into one. The political unification fostered the growth of a common language in Odisha- the "Odia Language". In the 13th and 14th century AD the Imperial Ganga rulers laid the foundation of modern Odisha by uniting all the territories into one in the name of "Sakalatkola" and made the Odia language the dominant speech in this land. In 15th century Kapilendradev used the word 'Odisha' and introduced 'Odia' as the Official Language of his empire. After that the Afghans, the Moghuls, the Marathas and the Britishers occupied Odisha and jeopardised the Odia language and Identity up to 1936. Only because of the language movement in 19th and 20th century it could have restored. After the introduction of Constitution in 1950 we became able to prepare an act 'The Orissa Official Language Act, 1954' on 14th Oct.1954 to use 'Odia' as our official language. But due to the apathy of administration yet we have to implement the act in its real terms. The Act has been amended a numerous time till date but due to the lack of modus operandi in supervision and award punishment still it is far behind the goal. In a protest to this greater cause "The Bhasa Andolan" has been organising 'Black Flag march'

every day since 13-04-2016 till date. Though the Odisha state was created on the basis of language in 1936, still the Odia people are fighting for their language in the 21st century before their own administration, in the age of knowledge and technology. The language movement in 19th and 20th century was in a British occupied state while the present language movement is in a province running under democracy of an independent country.

2. Odia Language before Official Language Act-1954.

2.1. Odia Language in the Pre-British Regime.

The people of this land were politically un-organised and culturally primitive up to the establishment of Somavamsis rule .The Somavamsis rulers spread the culture of Shaivism and score more political mileage to unite Odisha under single administration which laid the foundation of formative stage of Odia Identity on the basis of Odia language and culture. In this connection notable historian Prof.K .C .Panigrahi said that:-

"Up to the ninth-tenth century AD what is now known as Orissa consisted of three political and cultural units known as Kosala, Utkala and Kongoda and these three units were united under one rule by the Somavamsis. We have seen that Yajati-I occupied Orissa about 931AD and Yajati-II was requested by the people and ministers of the state to be the king of all these three distinct territories. From the reign of Yajati-II the capital of the Somavamsi

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kingdom was shifted from Kosala to the coastal region of Orissa. These political changes fostered the growth of a common language in Orissa. The people of the Kosala tract originally spoke a language which was akin to the Bhojapuri Prakrita, while the language of the coastal strip had family affinity with Magadhi. These two branches of Prachya Prakrita met and mingled in Orissa and formed a new language which came to be known as Oriya".⁰¹.

After Somavamsis the Imperial Gangas established their rule all over the Odisha and gave opportunity to the Odia people to enjoy independent Identity during 14th and 15th century AD. During the Ganga rule in Odisha Sanskrit language was patronised but the Odia Language has taken its place in the heart of the general public which resulted in the formation of Odia Identity on the basis of language. In the 15th century AD the Odia language under the patronisation of 'Kapilendradev' influenced our life, culture and administration to a great extent. In the words of historian Dr.N.K Sahu and others:-

"The accession of Kapilendradeva in 1435AD marks a turning point in the history and culture in Orissa. It is not only put an end to the long rule of the Gangas extending over a period of about one thousand years, but also brought about a significant change in the cultural life of the state. From that time onward the Oriya language was recognised in place of Sanskrit as the official language and Jagannath as the state deity".⁰².

After 1568 the Odisha state became a apple of discord between the Afghans and Moghuls. Though the hard earned identity was jeopardised the great litterateur like Balaram Das, Jagannath Das, Abhimanyu Samanta Simhara, Banamli Das, Brajanath Badajena, Upendra Bhanja, Dinakrushna Das, Arakshita Das, Gopalakrushna etc kept intact the linguistic movement of Odisha. Odia literature developed to a greater height without the patronisation of Afghans and Moghuls.

2.2. Odia Language in the British Regime.

In the year 1803 the British East India Company occupied Odisha in a piecemeal manner and administered the region in dividing Odisha into three parts in which the Southern part was tagged with Madras Presidency, the coastal region with Bengal and the western part with the Central province. The Odia people became linguistic minority group in the Telgu, Bengali and Hindi dominated provinces. Though the people of Odisha were politically disintegrated, their language and literature was one, their cultural and religious practices was one, which leads them towards the restoration of political, linguistic and cultural Identity in the first half of 20th century AD. For the formation of Identity the role of Language is more important. In this connection the editor of the journal 'Utkala Sahitya' and the General Secretary 'Utkala Sahitaya Samaj' Bishwanath Kar in his address on the occasion of second annual session of the above organisation said that; -

"Religion, Polity and language are the three important factors for the formation of a nation. Language is the most important factor which creates the network of strong relationships amongst the fellow countrymen by spreading the message of national importance and future plan for the achievement of own Identity".⁰³.

The notification made by the then Secretary of Bengal province in 1838 for the use of vernacular language in place of Persian in the court and revenue matter of the government since 01-01-1839, became a turning point in the history of language movement of Odisha. The establishment of English and vernacular schools, the Lord Hardinge resolution of 11th October 1844 and Woods Despatch of 1854 on education, the Lt. Governor George Campbell's scholarship scheme and reformed educational administration resulted in a gradual transformation of the mental horizon of the people of this land. From the organisational set up of Bhenkateswar Beu, the Raja of Katinga to the 'Utkala Sabha' and 'Utkal Sammilani', sacrifice of Madhusudan Das, Gourishankar Roy, Basudev Sudhaldev, Fakirmohan Senapati, Krushna Chandra Gajapati, Rajendra Narayan Bhanja Deo, Harihar Mardaraj, Sripati Mishra, Chandrashekhar Behara, Baikunthanath Pujari, Nilamani Vidyaratna and support of A. L. H. Fraser, T. E. Ravenshaw, John Beams etc was the fighting for language based Odia Identity only. It was felt by every fellowmen of this country that language is the important part of nationalism and identity. They fought for the cause which resulted in the Language movement of 1870 and the Sambalpur language movement of 1895 -1905. This language movement was meant for the restoration of Odia language in official use and for medium of instruction in Schools of Odisha. Regarding the importance of language in public life M. M. Malaviya quotes that;-

"It is highly important that Justice should be administered in the language familiar to the judge, but it is of no less importance that it should be administered in a language familiar...to the people at large; and it is easier for the judge to acquire the language of the people than for the people to acquire the language of the judge".⁰⁴.

So it was the Odia language which played an important role to unify the dis-integrated people of Odisha. In 1936 the separate state of Odisha was created on the basis of language. This movement was an organised effort of Odia linguistic community to establish their linguistic identity. According to Santosh Kumar Barik in his article "The Oriya Language: Its past, present and future-A General survey" quotes that;-

"Many external forces opposed its continuance and made conspiracies to wipe it out. But this language has survived despite the conspiracies and criticism which bears ample testimony to its inner strength and resilience".⁰⁵.

2.3. Odia Language After 1936

The separate state of Odisha was created on the basis of favourable report submitted by Sinha Committee in 1920 and Phillip-Duff Committee in 1924 and the pressure built by Bhubanananda Das and other members of Bihar-Odisha Assembly. From 1936 to 1946 the Odisha administration was placed under the premiers. Though our State was created on the basis of language no efforts have been initiated during this time to use the Odia language in the administration. The dream of Odia nationalists who fought a long battle and restored Odia identity in 1936 remain a far cry.

2.4. Odia Language after Independence.

After independence the MLA of Baragarh –East constituency Mr. Laxinarayan Mishra had placed a proposal before the Odisha Legislative Assembly on 1st April 1948 to use ‘Odia’ as the official language of Odisha to which Mr. Bose the MLA of Cuttack vehemently opposed with the support of the then Law Minister Mr. Nityananda Kanungo. In this situation the use of ‘Odia’ as the official language became a distant dream.

On the 12th day of May 1950 Nabakrushna Choudhury became the Chief Minister of Odisha and as a popular measure of his statesmanship, he took interest to run the state administration in the people’s language. All the higher officials were against this proposal as most of them were non-odia people. In this context Mr. Padmacharan Nayak stated in his book ‘Anirvana’ that:-

“The then (1950) Chief Secretary raised his voice against the above proposal with a plea that; while the vernacular language has not been used as the official language in the other States of India, why so eagerness is in the Odisha? This will create problems in the communication to the Central Government and the office of Accountant General. ⁰⁶.

In spite of the apathetic attitude of higher officials in the year 1952 Nabakrushna Choudhury took necessary steps to prepare an English-Odia Administrative Glossary. Though all officials were against the introduction of Odia language in administration the Hon’ble. CM Nabakrushna Choudhury started to give his note in govt. files in Odia language from 23rd April 1954. In this year the Orissa Official Language Act, 1954 was passed on 14th October. To implement this act in real term steps were taken to prepare Odia Key-Board and Type Writer. In this context Mr. Padmacharan Nayak stated in his book ‘Anirvana’ that:-

“To implement the Odisha Official Language Act a committee was constituted under the chairmanship of Gajendra Mitra, Director, Department of Industries where Manmohan Choudhury was a member. On the recommendation of this committee Key Board was prepared and order was placed before the Remington company in 1956 to manufacture and supply Odia Typewriter. ⁰⁷.

Notwithstanding the initiative and statesmanship of the then Chief Minister Nabakrushna Choudhury all the officials became disloyal to the public and created stumbling blocks on the way of the implementation of the said act. According to the statement of Surendra Mohanty in ‘Surendra Bichitra’:-

“In fact the history of Odisha Official Language Act-1954 is tragic in nature. Most probably it is rare in the history of bureaucratic red-tapism. ⁰⁸.

“To bring back the glory of Odia language from exile, either we have to convert the infertile brains of Odisha secretariat or to keep them out from the scene. A community cannot wait for an uncertain period at the vested interest of a powerful bureaucracy. ⁰⁹.

This observation clearly reflects the apathetic attitude of bureaucrats of Odisha for the use of ‘Odia language’ in state administration after independence while the modern

human being is professing; “Government is of the people, by the people and for the people”. During the British administration the Bengali peoples were against the Odia language but after independence our own people are betraying since the inception of the Act till date. The act have been amended for about five times in the year 1963, 1985, 2016 & 2018 but till now Odia language is neglected in the Odisha administration and public instruction. Though the worthy predecessors of Odia community could achieve success in restoring Odia in administration and public instruction during the British regime the present generation is deprived from the same in 21st century AD when democracy prevailed.

3. Constitutional Provision for the Official Language.

Article 345: The state legislature of a state may by law adopt any one or more of the languages in use in the State or Hindi as the language or languages to be used for all or any of the official purposes of that State.

Article 347: If the President is satisfied that a substantial proportion of the population of a State desire the use of any language spoken by them to be recognised by that State, direct that such language shall also be officially recognised throughout that state or any part thereof for such purpose as he may specify.

Article 350: Every person shall be entitled to submit a representation for the redress of any grievance to any officer or authority of the Union or a State in any of the languages used in the Union or in the State, as the case may be.

The provision in Article-345&347 always justified for the Odia community while Article-350 is a basic right to them. On the basis of these provision ‘The Odisha Official Language Act’ have been implemented in the state but in practice it is now only a paper tiger and the Odia people are getting deprived of their long desired fruit.

4. The Odisha Official Language Act.

4.1. The Orissa Official Language Act, 1954. (14th Oct.1954)

The Odisha Official Language Act is in operative in Odisha since 1954. The important provision of the Act and the Amendments are as details below:-

It is expedient to provide for the adoption of Oriya as the language to be used for all or any of the official purposes of the State of Orissa.

Sec-1(2)-It Extends to the Whole of Orissa.

(3)-It shall come into force at once.

Sec-2(1)-Without prejudice to the provisions of Article-346 and 347 of the constitution Oriya shall be the language to be used for all or any of the official purposes of the State of Orissa.

(2)-The State Government may, by notification, direct that in any specified area and with effect from any specified date Oriya shall be used in respect of such official purposes as may be specified in the notification.

Sec-3- After notification Oriya language to be used for all Bills introduced, Acts passed and Amendments by the Orissa Legislative Assembly, all Ordinances promulgated by the Governor under Art-213 of our constitution and all Orders,

Rules, Regulations, Bye-laws etc issued by State Government under the constitutional provision shall be Oriya.

4.2. The Orissa Official Language (Amendment) Act, 1963, (30th Oct.1963)

Section 3A inserted in the Act. Having provision- the English language may as from the 26th day of January 1965, continue to be used in addition to Oriya for the transaction of business in Legislature of the State of Orissa.

4.3. The Orissa Official Language (Amendment) Act, 1985, (23rd Sept.1985)

Section-2(Amendment)-Where Oriya shall be used as the language for Official purposes the Oriya numerals shall not be used and international form of Indian numerals should be used.

4.4. The Odisha Official Language (Amendment) Act, 2016, (06th Oct.2016)

Insertion of New sections 4 and 5.

Section-4-The State Government may, within such period, in such manner and by such authority, as may be prescribed in the rules made under this Act, review and monitor whether the direction contained in the notification issued under sub-section(2) of section 2 has been effectively implemented.

Section-5-The State Government may make rules to carry out the purposes of the Act.

4.5. The Odisha Official Language (Amendment) Act, 2018, (27th April 2018)

Insertion of New section 4A.

Section-4A-The State Government may prescribe suitable measures in the rules to award incentives to officials or Departments for extensive use of the official language and also to punish the erring officials or departments.

4.6. The Odisha Official Language (Second Amendment) Act, 2018, (31st Oct.2018)

Section-4A (Amendment)-'Odia' before Official Language 'Or both' after Department to be inserted in the 2018 Act.

The Sec-1 of the Act says that; It extends to the whole of Orissa and (sub-sec-2) and it shall come into force at once. Sec-2(1) says; Odia shall be the language to be used for all or any of the official purposes of the State of Odisha. The official work in Odia at the base level offices were going on in response to the provision of the Act but after the insertion of Section 3A in 1963 having provision to use English language from the 26th day of January 1965, in addition to Odia for the transaction of business in Legislature of the State of Orissa, the English language occupied the dominant place. Though provision has been made in 2016 in the Section-4 of the act for review and monitoring of its effective implementation. It is observed that no monitoring and supervision has been made and the act has not been implemented to its real term. After so many hue and cries in the public the government has again inserted a new section -4A in 2018 to the act with a provision of incentives to the officials or Departments for extensive use of the official language and also to punish the erring officials or departments. But it is a matter of great concern that due to the lack of modus operandi in the incentive and punishment provision there is no more development in the implementation of the Act till date. As a

protest to this the language movement of 21st century AD has been started under the banner of 'Bhasa Andolan' since 13-04-2016.

5. Early Study on the" Orissa Official Language Act, 1954'.

5.1. Prof. Banshidhar Mohanty (1989) in 'Odia Bhasa Andolan':-

suggested that; to implement the above act training to officials for noting, drafting in Odia is necessary. The entire official should talk with the people in Odia language. To use English language is a complete betrayal to the People of Odisha.

5.2. On 21st June 1995 'Institute of Language, Literature and Culture" (ILLAC) was organised a Seminar on the topic "Odisha Official Language Act" where different views were generated and some important out of that is;-

➤ Dr. Aravinda Pattanaik said; - We have 1, 85,000 words in the 'Purnachandra Odia Bhasakosa' and can be utilised for the implementation of the Act. Further he opined that 'with the use of Odia as Official Language, the State administration will be people friendly. It will encourage people's participation in the development'.

➤ Dr. Deviprasanna Pattanaik said: - There should be a state language policy for the development of people.

➤ Mr. Manmohan Choudhury said: The Act is yet to be properly implemented due to the apathetic attitude of administration. Though the officials and political representative are living on the tax payer, still they are betraying. Further he said that the neck-tie culture is controlling the secretariat administration and one day it will drag into the extinction of our language and culture.

➤ Mr. Sahadev sahu(ICS) put forth a view that, the Orissa Official Language Act should be implemented without any exception, otherwise it will failed again as was the order of 1968. He also said, if Odia language will be the official language for only 10 years it will generate more interest than the 110 years of(1837-1947) English use.

➤ Mr. Tara Dutta(ICS) emphasized that, 'Odia is the peoples language and should be used for the governance of Odia people'.

➤ Dr. Ranjita Nayak opined that 'Computer should be in Odia language and necessary steps should be taken by the concern agencies.

5.3. Mr. Gajanan Mishara; Writing an article in 'Samaj' in December 2014- advocated for the use of Odia language in subordinate judiciary. In March 2015 he appealed openly to the people of Odisha for a indefinite hunger strike from the 1st April 2015 for the implementation of the Act. Later on in September 2016 he expressed his agony on the ineffective steps of Ministerial committee scheduled on 01-08-2015 and suggested penal provision in the act.

5.3. Mr.Hrudayaballav Dash" 23/08/2014 in 'Samaj'- gave a call to the government for the implementation of the act and said that patronisation of administration is necessary.

5.5. Mr.Panchanan Kanungo, Samaj, 15/09/2015; said extensive use of Odia language in school and college curriculum is required in addition to the office administration.

- 5.6. Mr. Subhashish Panigrahi, Samaj, 13/04/2014, 25/12/2014, and 21/02/2015 advocated for the use of Odia in technical field along with the development of technology to facilitate odia language for its extensive use.

All the above views between 1989-2016 are genuine in their spirit and restricted to the implementation of the Act. But in present days more feathers has been added to the act. In spite of all provisions the state administration is apathetic to the matter what is reflected in the above views.

6. 'The Orissa Official Language Act, 1954'. (14th Oct.1954): Success and Failures.

6.1. Government Initiative to Implement the Act.

The Odisha Official Language Act has a provision in the sub-section (3) of section -1 that it shall come in to force at once and in the sub-section (2) of said act is that it extends to the whole of Odisha. But in practice it has no teeth and took shelter in the red-taping process. Though it was not introduced to its real term and conditions there was amendment to this act in 1963 termed as "The Orissa Official Language (Amendment) Act, 1963", to use English language in addition to Odia for the transaction of business in Legislature of the State of Odisha. After this amendment all the officials used English language only and shown stepmother attitude towards the peoples language of Odisha which has given an Identity to this community on language basis. In response to the said act a notification vide No:8189/Dt.14.04.1966 was issued by the Political & Services Department, Govt. of Orissa, that "Oriya shall be used in the whole of the state of Orissa in respect of the official purposes in the Departments of Community Development & PanchayatiRaj, Revenue, Tribal&Rural Welfare, Education and Forestry with effect from 16.05.1966." As this order was not carried out properly by the officials another notification vide. No: 7113/Dt.16-04-1968 was issued by the same department with a modification to the previous one that; "Oriya shall be used in all offices of the Heads of Departments within the meaning of Rule 20 of the Orissa Service Code and in office subordinate to them excepting the office of the Registrar, Orissa High Court and offices of the district judges and offices subordinate there to in the whole of the state of Orissa". Again a notification vide No.7152/Dt.29.03.1985 was issued by GA department for the effective use of the said Act. In supersession to all previous notifications issued under the sub-section-2 of the Act, the State Government do hereby direct that with effect from 1st Day of April 1985 Oriya shall be used in all offices of the State Government excepting Judiciary. After that the act was again amended in 1985 and 2016 and section 4 and 5 was inserted to it with the provision of review and monitor of the implementation of the above said act. After the amendment of 1985 a notification was issued in 1994 by the School and Education Department to introduce Odia as the compulsory examinable subject in English medium schools. In the month of April 1995 an order was issued from the Chief Minister Office (CMO) that all the files placed before the Chief Minister must be prepared in Odia language. In the year 1999 a notification was issued by the Revenue Department in which it was stated that; in spite of various official notifications it is observed that the noting and drafting in most of the files are in English. This is a matter of regret and should be end at once. Further all the employees are advised to follow the

'Administrative Glossary' prepared in 1997 by the Law Department, Government of Odisha. Another notification was issued in 2005 by the Assembly Secretariat that all the files, drafts, proposals, proceedings and written communication will be made in Odia language. But all the efforts were in vain. As all the notifications and directions were not fruitful in their spirit. Again order was issued by the GA Department in 2012,2013 &2014 seeking a progress report from the Heads of Departments and District Collectors about the steps taken to implement 'Odia' as the Official Language .

In the process of implementation of the Act the "Odisha Official Language Committee" was formed in 1969. Prof. Bansidhar Mohanty said that:

"The "Odisha Official Language Committee" formed in 1969 under the chairmanship of Law Minister had translated various rules and regulations of Government. The committee was constituted by taking specialists in the field of science, Language, literature, Law and others to make the translation process successful." ¹⁰.

"Though the "Odisha Official Language Committee" is working in translation and other works by appointing special officers and its progress was very slow. To implement the Act separate Directorate should be created to expedite the work". ¹¹.

On the implementation of this Act Prof. Mohanty with great concern stated that:-

"During the British rule in Odisha 'Odia' language was used in the Revenue and Excise Department, Sub-registrar Office, Tsahalis Office and also petition in the courts. The arguments in courts were also in the Odia language. But after independence the use of 'Odia' as an official language is not to our expectation". ¹².

6.2. Legal Issues for the Implementation of the Act.

A Writ Petition was filed before High court of Odisha in 2007 against the refusal of registrar, Civil Court, Bolangir to provide a copy of the judgement in Odia language in which the appellate court disposed the case having a direction to the said Registrar to reconsider the application of the petitioner under section 173(3) of the Code of Civil Procedure.

Another Writ Petition was filed before High court of Odisha in 2012 against the refusal of Civil Judge (Sr.Divn.), Titilagarh to provide a copy of the written statement of the defendant in Odia language in which the appellate court disposed the case having a direction to the said Civil Judge (Sr.Divn.), Titilagarh to reconsider the application of the petitioner under section 173(3) of the Code of Civil Procedure within fifteen days.

Again in 2012 a Public Interest Litigation (PIL) was filed with a prayer to issue order for the proper implementation of Odisha Official Language Act-1954 and to take appropriate legal action against the officials who violate the provision in the use of Odia as Official language. In this case the court has directed the petitioner to file a representation before the Secretary, General Administration, Government of Odisha with a permission to approach this court if it is not considered after eight weeks of the filing of representation.

6.3. Technical problems on the way of Implementation of the Act

During the twentieth century the use of Odia Typewriter in offices could expedite the implementation of the Act. On the advent of computer the use of Typewriter was neglected, though there was provision for External software like Leap office, Akruti etc. The use of 'Odia' in office got a severe blow and English occupied the throne. Though in present scenario computer has inbuilt odia language like 'Unicode' still we are far away from the implementation the Act only because of our apathetic attitude and lack of awareness. Special training to the officials with the help of language specialists, appointment of translator and Odia language specialist in offices may accelerate the process of the implementation of this Act. Due to the lack of knowledge in Odia language our officials are translating 'issue' as 'Nirgamana' and so many others. Now after the introduction of "The Odisha Official Language (Amendment) Act, 2018, having the provision of award incentives to officials or Departments for extensive use of the official language and also to punish the erring officials or departments, it is observed that neither a single department or official is interested to receive incentives or have a fear to be punished. It happened due to the absence of modus operandi of the punishment provision and supervision thereof.

7. Present Day Language movement in Odisha.

After observing the apathetic attitude of state administration the elite people of Odia community have taken the shelter of journalism to raise their voice against the injustice and betrayal done to them as discussed above in the literature review. Then the people resorted to organised movement and formed various organisations for the purpose. The 'Bhasa Surakshya Sammilani', 'Bhasa Sangram Samiti', 'Samaj Andolan' and 'Bhasa Andolan' are the most important out of them. The hunger strike of Gajanan Mishra, the demand of 'Bhasa Surakshya Sammilani' under the chairmanship of Baishnav Charan Parida, 'Bhasa Sangram Samiti' under Shankarsan Parida and others, 'Samaj Andolan' under the chairmanship of Kulamani Nayak and 'Bhasa Andolan' under the chairmanship of Subhas Chandra Pattanaik awaken the Government of Odisha again to implement the Odisha Official Language Act. In this connection a Ministerial Committee was formed to chalk out the Modus Operandi for the implementation of the said Act in real term. In this committee, members were taken from various field of specialisation along with representation from the organisations fighting for the above cause. In this committee as a representative of 'Bhasa Sangram Samiti' Subhas Chandra Pattanaik has placed some proposals for the amendment of the above Act for effective implementation. But his proposal for the punishment provision to the erring officials was kept in bay. In a protest to the betrayal of Ministerial committee the 'Bhasa Andolan' under the chairmanship of Subhas Chandra Pattanaik has started 'Black Flag March' on 13-04-2016 with a demand of penal provision in the Odisha Official Language Act to ensure proper implementation of governance of Odisha in Odia. As a scheduled programme the flag march commences everyday at 05.00PM outside the Assembly and culminates at Madhubabu's statue near the Governor House square after paying floral tribute to the Grand old man and the chief architect of modern Odisha. The 'Odisha Official Language (Amendment) Act, 2016' did not incorporated the proposal

of penal provision placed by Mr. Pattanaik. So the flag march got support of general public and the Government of Odisha again amended the Act in 2018. The Odisha Official Language (Amendment) Act, 2018 newly inserted the section 4A that; The State Government may prescribe suitable measures in the rules to award incentives to officials or Departments for extensive use of the official language and also to punish the erring officials or departments. With this amendment the Government of Odisha declared the extensive use of Odia language in every official transaction from April 2019. But in practice no department or officials are using 'Odia' as the Official language and no department or official have been punished for the violation of this Act till date. It is happening due to the absence of terms and conditions and details of penal provision in the Act. So keeping the stand intact 'Bhasa Andolan' under the chairmanship of Mr. Subhas Chandra Pattanaik 'Black Flag March' has been organising everyday to fulfil basic aim and objectives of the Act, at the greater interest of general public to be governed in the peoples language. The Andolan or Language movement is continuing though we are in the 21st Century where technological knowledge exploration is in the maximum height.

'Odia' language is the identity of the peoples of Odisha as defined by H.Giles & P.Johnson on the Identity theory of H.Tajfel, 'Language is a salient marker of group membership and social identity'. This theory has been successfully experimented through the language movement of Odisha in 19th and 20th century. The political and cultural unification of Somavansi rulers foster the growth of a common language in Odisha- the "Odia Language". Patronisation of Odia language by 'Kapilendradev' brought a revolutionary change in the history of Odia identity and formation of Odisha. Now a day in 21st century we are lacking behind this achievement. After creation of separate Odisha state in 1936 and also after independence the people in administration of this land did not taken proper care for the use of Odia language in administration and due to this we are suffering till date and the 'Black Flag March' is going on. The Act is now a toothless paper tiger only. After 1947 Odia peoples have the Acts, rules and regulations, law and administration, institute and technology, education and resources but their mother language is far away from administration. But the role of language for a community is most important. According to the view of M.T.Cicero "Nothing is so akin to our natural feelings as the rhythms and sounds of voices. They rouse and inflame us, calm us and soothe us and often lead us to joy and sadness".

8. Conclusion

On the above discussion the inference derived is that;

- The strong Somavamsi administration could unite the people of this land politically and culturally which resulted in the origin and development of Odia Language in 10th century AD.
- The strong administration and statesmanship of Kapilendradev could create the "Odisha" state and made the peoples language as the Official Language of Odisha in 1435AD.
- The strong protest of Odia people could put mounting pressure on the British administration for the use of vernacular language in the court and revenue matters.
- The organised language movement in 19th and 20th century could restore Odia identity in 1936.

But in modern Odisha Odia people forget to use the same canon for its development as soon it took birth. As the scholars stated above for the proper implementation of this Act, besides the training, technology, development of sources the administrative patronisation is the most important factor. In this regard I am agree with the views of above scholars. The proposal of Mr.Gajanan Mishra (Samaj, Odia Bhasa Aainra karyakari kebe?) and Mr.Subhas Pattanaik demand for penal provision is very noteworthy and only because of that shortcoming the Act is yet to be properly implemented. The present day language movement is the consequence of the lack of statesmanship in administration and the infringement of the basic right of Odia community. The language movement in 19th and 20th century was in a British occupied state while the present language movement is in a province running under democracy of an independent country.

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